

Synthesis and characterization of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of tetraaza- and hexaazamacrocycles derived from α -diketones and polyamines

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Abstract : Complexes of the types [NiL](NO₃)₂, [CuL]Cl₂ and [ZnL]Cl₂ (where L = hexaazamacrocycle having 18-membered ring) have been synthesized by the 2+2 cyclocondensation of α -diketones such as 3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil with 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane in the presence of metal ions as templates. 1+1 Cyclocondensation of α -diketones with 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane in the presence of metal ions leads to macrocyclic complexes of the type [CuL]Cl₂ and [ZnL]Cl₂ (where L = tetraazamacrocycle having 12-membered ring). These have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, magnetic measurements, IR, electronic and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II).

The branch of macrocyclic chemistry involving the synthesis of a variety of metal complexes has developed rapidly during the past few years¹. Due to their biological relevance transition metal ions have generally been used as templates and a variety of tetraaza-² and hexaazamacrocycles³ have been synthesized. We report in the present paper the template synthesis of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of tetraaza- and hexaazamacrocycles derived from α -diketones (4,4'-dimethylbenzil or 3,4-hexanedione) and polyamines (1,5-diamino-3-azapentane or 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane).

Results and discussion

Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 18-membered hexaazamacrocycles have been synthesized by 2+2 cyclocondensation of α -diketones such as 3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil with 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane in the presence of metal ions as templates (Scheme 1).

Cu^{II} complexes of 12-membered tetraazamacrocycles having one α -diimine unit have been synthesized by 1 : 1 molar reactions of α -diketones such as 3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil with 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane using Cu^{II} as template :

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of hexaazamacrocycles.

By the similar template procedure, reaction of 4,4'-dimethylbenzil with 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane in the presence of ZnCl₂ in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio has yielded Zn^{II} complex of a tetraazamacrocycle.

All the resulting macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} are stable at room temperature. These are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, methanol, acetonitrile and nitrobenzene but are soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. They do not have sharp melting points but decompose on heating at higher temperatures.

Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions in DMSO of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are observed in the range 57–85 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating their 2 : 1 electrolytic behaviour (Table 1) except the complex [Zn{(p-tolyl)₂[12]dieneN₄}Cl₂] which is non-electrolyte⁴.

show a broad band at ~16500 cm⁻¹ due to ligand field transitions. This broad band contains all the possible *d-d* transitions consistent with the square planar geometry of copper(II) complexes⁶. The spectra of Cu^{II} complexes also exhibit absorption bands at ~29000 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to π-π* transitions or charge transfer.

IR spectra of the complexes exhibit bands in the region 3280–3300 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to νN–H vibrations⁷. All the complexes show absorption bands at 1550–1650 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to νC=N. None of the complexes exhibits bands at 1700 cm⁻¹ indicating the absence of unreacted C=O group⁸. The complexes of the macrocycles derived from 4,4'-dimethylbenzil exhibit bands in the region 1410–1610 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to νC=C of phenyl groups⁹.

The observed values of magnetic moments for the complexes at room temperature are given in Table 1. Ni^{II} complex possesses μ_{eff} 3.01 B.M. which is consistent

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of hexaazamacrocycles and tetraazamacrocycles derived from α-diketones and polyamines

Complex	Colour and decomposition temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Molar conductances (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
			M	N	Cl		
[Ni(Et ₄ [18]tetraeneN ₆)](NO ₃) ₂	Purple 185	57	10.61 (10.76)	15.57 (15.41)	-	85	3.01
[Cu(Et ₂ [12]dieneN ₄)Cl ₂]	Green 150	42	17.61 (17.71)	15.92 (15.61)	14.50 (14.27)	57	1.92
[Cu{(p-tolyl) ₂ [12]dieneN ₄ }Cl ₂]	Green 180	78	13.21 (13.15)	11.80 (11.60)	9.43 (9.51)	65	2.10
[Cu(Et ₄ [18]tetraeneN ₆)Cl ₂]	Blue 215	47	12.80 (12.79)	16.69 (16.91)	20.09 (19.76)	78	2.42
[Cu{(p-tolyl) ₄ [18]tetraeneN ₆ }Cl ₂]	Blue 235	67	8.61 (8.52)	11.53 (11.27)	14.55 (14.68)	72	1.98
[Zn{(p-tolyl) ₂ [12]dieneN ₄ }Cl ₂]	White 190	75	13.17 (13.48)	11.36 (11.55)	14.54 (14.62)	17	-
[Zn{(p-tolyl) ₄ [18]tetraeneN ₆ }Cl ₂]	White 235	71	8.87 (8.75)	7.64 (7.49)	9.68 (9.48)	66	-

Electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complex of hexaazamacrocycle and Cu^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles have been recorded. Ni^{II} complex exhibits absorption bands at 16500 and 27000 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively⁵. Thus, the electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex supports the distorted octahedral geometry with D_{4h} symmetry. Cu^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles derived from α-diketones and 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane

with high-spin octahedral environment around the metal ion. The μ_{eff} values for Cu^{II} complexes are observed in the range 1.92–2.42 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron. Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic¹⁰.

FAB mass spectrum of one representative complex [Cu(Et₄[18]tetraeneN₆)Cl₂] was recorded using NBA matrix and is reproduced in Fig. 1. Peaks at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. The complex exhibits peaks at *m/z* 495 (15.8%) due to the molecular

ion (M^+) and at m/z 362 (10.5%) due to the macrocycle (L^+). This confirms the formation of the macrocyclic complex. Bastida *et al.*¹¹ have reported an intense peak due to the macrocycle in the mass spectra of lanthanide(III) complexes of the macrocycle derived from 2,6-bis(2-formylphenoxy)methylpyridine and 1,2-diaminoethane.

Path B. In this pathway two C_2H_5 groups are removed from the molecular ion (M^+) to give a peak at m/z 437 (31.6%). Simultaneous loss of remaining two C_2H_5 groups gives a peak at m/z 379 (5.3%). Loss of metal ion and two chloride groups gives a peak at m/z 246 (5.2%) due to the species II.

Fig. 1. Mass spectrum of the complex $[Cu(Et_4[18]tetraeneN_6)Cl_2]$.

Alkaline earth metal complexes of the macrocycles derived from furan-2,5-dicarbaldehyde and 3,6,9-trioxaundecane-1,11-diamine or 1,5-bis(2-aminophenoxy)-3-oxapentane have been reported to exhibit peaks corresponding to the macrocycles¹². In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ion and the macrocycle, the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycle and its complex. The fragmentation pattern of the complex is given in Scheme 2. There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex :

Path A. In this pathway, the metal ion and two chloride groups are removed from the molecular ion (M^+) and the peak due to the macrocycle (L^+) is obtained at m/z 362 (10.5%). Successive loss of four C_2H_5 groups gives peaks at m/z 333 (5.3%), 304 (10.5%), 275 (5.2%) and finally at 246 (5.2%) due to the species II.

Experimental

$Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck), $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (B.D.H.) and $ZnCl_2$ (Fluka) were of A.R. grade. 4,4'-Dimethylbenzil (Aldrich), 3,4-hexanedione (Aldrich), 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane (Fluka) and 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane (Fluka) were used as supplied. *n*-Butanol (B.D.H.) was distilled before use.

Nickel and zinc were determined volumetrically by EDTA using Eriochrome Black T as indicator. Copper was determined iodometrically using starch indicator. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as $AgCl$. Conductances of the complexes were measured with the help of a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304 using 10^{-3} M solutions in DMSO. The Gouy method was used for the determination of magnetic susceptibilities. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded in the region $4000-400$ cm^{-1}

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of the complex $[Cu(Et_4[18]tetraeneN_6)]Cl_2$.

on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded (in DMSO) on a Jasco-7800 UV/VIS spectrophotometer. FAB mass spectra of the complexes were recorded at CDRI, Lucknow on a JEOL SX 102/DA-600 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mV) as the FAB gas.

(i) *Synthesis of Ni^{II} complex of hexaazamacrocycle derived from 3,4-hexanedione and 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane* : $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (1.31 mmol, 0.382 g) was dissolved in 20 ml of *n*-butanol and to this a solution of 3,4-hexanedione (2.62 mmol, 0.299 g in 20 ml *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. It was followed by the addition of a solution of 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane (2.62 mmol, 0.270 g in 20 ml *n*-butanol) dropwise with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for 5 h. A purple solid appeared which was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Similarly, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of other hexaazamacrocycles derived from 3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil and 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane were

synthesized.

(ii) *Synthesis of Cu^{II} complex of tetraazamacrocycle derived from 3,4-hexanedione and 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane* : $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (3.24 mmol, 0.554 g) was dissolved in 20 ml *n*-butanol and to this a solution of 3,4-hexanedione (3.24 mmol, 0.370 g in 20 ml *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. It was followed by the addition of a solution of 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane (3.24 mmol, 0.475 g in 20 ml *n*-butanol) dropwise with stirring. Stirring was continued for 5 h. A green solid appeared which was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Similarly, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of the tetraazamacrocycle derived from 4,4'-dimethylbenzil and 1,8-diamino-3,6-diazaoctane were synthesized.

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References

1. A. K. Singh, S. Chandra and S. Banilwal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 84; S. K. Gupta and Y. S. Kushwah, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 2019; S. Chandra and S. D. Sharma, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 732; P. B. Samnani, V. Manjula and P. K. Bhattacharya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 1078; S. Chandra and K. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 775; T. A. Khan, S. S. Hasan, N. Jahan, A. K. Mohamed and K. S. Islam, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1090.
2. P. Comba, S. M. Luther, O. Mass, H. Pritzkow and Annette Vielfort, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 2335; N. F. Curtis, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2001, **27**, 317; T. J. Hubin, J. M. McCormick, N. W. Alcock and D. H. Busch, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 435; A. K. Mohamed, K. S. Islam, S. S. Hasan and S. Mohamed, *Transition Metal Chem.*, 1999, **24**, 198; R. Saraswat and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 493; K. S. Siddiqui and N. Nishat, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1999, **29**, 297.
3. W. U. Malik, R. Bembi and R. Singh, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 369; A. Tabassum, S. H. Rafiqi, N. Nishat, F. Arjmand and S. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1237; D. P. Singh, N. Shishodia, B. P. Yadav and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 287.
4. N. W. Alcock, K. P. Balakrishnan, P. Moore and H. A. A. Omar, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1987, 545; R. W. Hay, D. P. Piplani and B. Jeragh, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1951; J. Lewis and T. D. O. Dongohue, *J. Chem. Soc.*,

- Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 743.
5. M. S. Holtman and S. C. Cummings, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 660.
 6. M. Fujiwara, Y. Nakajima, T. Matsushita and T. Shono, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 1589.
 7. D. E. Fenton, B. P. Murphy, A. J. Leong, L. F. Lindoy, A. Bashall and M. McPartlin, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1987, 2543.
 8. M. G. B. Drew, A. H. bin Othman, P. D. A. McIlroy and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 2507.
 9. W. A. Welsh, G. J. Reynolds and P. M. Henry, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 2558.
 10. D. P. Singh and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 266; P. R. Shukla, R. Rastogi, N. Ahmed and G. Narain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **65**, 663.
 11. E. Bertolo, R. Bastida, A. De Blas, D. E. Fenton, C. Lodeiro, A. Macias, A. Rodriguez and T. R. Blas, *J. Inclusion Phenom. Macro. Chem.*, 1999, **35**, 191.
 12. D. H. Cook and D. E. Fenton, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1979, 810.